

To Explore the Impact of Knowledge Hiding Towards Entrepreneurial Intentions - An Empirical Study of Software Industry

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Abstract

Knowledge is the basic pillar or foundation for getting a competitive advantage. Taking, loading, distributing (sharing) and using the knowledge has progressively become a vital part of most firms' knowledge management approach. Moreover, there are many studies founded on knowledge sharing but the concept of knowledge hiding is still untouched. Therefore, no study has been conducted to check the response of behavior intentions and knowledge hiding of individuals. This research study will contribute to the literature gap by providing a theoretical or empirical outline based on literature appraisal. Individuals working in different organizations hide knowledge from colleagues to maintain own portfolio. It is a quantitative study. Companies that run-in software business or industry is considered amongst the knowledge founded in which employees required to possess particular knowledge and skills.

Key Terms; *knowledge hiding, Rationalized Hiding, Playing Dumb, Evasive Hiding, entrepreneurial intentions, coworker relationship, the software industry*

1. INTRODUCTION

In spite of the efforts of the advancement as well as enhancement of knowledge transfer within the organizations system, achievements and success have been stable or elusive. It's clear that the individual that may be an employee shows their unwillingness to share knowledge across the organizational practices level. In recent times an emergent body of literature highlights few of the difficulties which concern to sharing of knowledge at the workplace, like the issues of enhancing of knowledge within virtual based teams. While knowledge hiding is interpreted as a low-base-rate occasion (Connelly et al., 2012), it signifies the main risk or a threat to the performance of personalities or in addition to organizations (Černe et al., 2014; Peng, 2013). It delays the development and effectiveness of organizations in line for the absence of innovation (Baer, 2012). Regardless of this, there is minor practical research on knowledge hiding, its backgrounds, and penalties in organizations.

The impression of knowledge hiding in firms can be defined by this wonder. Hiding is distinct as it's individual's careful struggling for hiding a knowledge demanded through another individual. So, in conditions where there is an explicit appeal for knowledge or the opposed one hides it, or knowledge hiding (KH) actions happens (Connelly et.al, 2012; Witten Baum 2004). Meanwhile, knowledge hiding happens between colleagues, the excellence of the relationship between them is very vital. It is too important to distinguish how an individual reply to a knowledge appeal or a request that is prepared by another colleague. Mutual or Shared relationships usually happen due to a tacit common exchange among individuals in organizations (Blau, 1964). In a structurally shared relationship, there are few of the expectations that require an interpersonal trust somewhere individuals may share their knowledge the additional or more. In added arguments, an imperative feature influencing this sort of conduct or behavior is the power of relationships among the knowledge demanding manager and knowledge demanding individuals (Yukl et al., 1996).

Organizational or Structural Innovation is a theme of thoughtful academic, theoretical and strategy attention for several periods. The 'creative organizations' are considered for a tinier era or for a short time, but possibly more deeply (Miles and Green, 2010). Organizational components can bring added innovations and appreciate improved performance if they conquer dominant network locations that deliver contact to new knowledge advanced by other elements. This outcome, conversely, depends on units' or organizational elements absorptive volume, or their ability to positively duplicate new knowledge. Although IT is used to deliver a network to inspire sharing, there is also the credit of the position of the face- to- face interaction for sharing tacit knowledge.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Knowledge

According to Davenport and Prusak (1998, p.5), knowledge can be defined as, “it’s a fluid combination of enclosed experiences, values, expert’s visions and appropriate information that deliver a framework for accessing and joining new information and experiences”. According to Lam and Bavik (2015), knowledge hiding is also defined as when an individual provides fewer information as a contribution to the organizational or managerial knowledge. Connelly et al., (2012) and Peng, (2013) stated that a behavior of knowledge hiding may bring a negative or positive impact, in case of negative it may bring a lot of distortions in collaboration level of organizations like problems in new idea generation, implementation of policies or rules as well as a negative perception on an individual to contribution of knowledge towards furthermore work situations, in a positive aspects knowledge hiding may be beneficial to hide the private rights of an organization.

Knowledge is the visions, identifications, and applied knowledge that individuals own. It is the Central source that lets individuals’ purpose logically. It can be specified that Knowledge is an unseen or intangible talent or asset, in which its achievement includes compound reasoning Procedures of awareness, education, communication, suggestion and reasoning (Epetimehin and Ekundayo, 2011). Allee (1997) declares that knowledge develops significant effects when it is understood in the superior setting of culture, which changes out of principles and attitude. Sveiby (1997) labels knowledge as the size to act on information and thus make it appreciated or value able, so knowledge can be supposed to be incompetent if not used. In organizations, knowledge develops surrounded not only in papers or sources but also in organizational procedures, developments, practices, standards, and philosophies.

Knowledge can be segregated into two diverse types, as Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) defined knowledge as current in two proportions – tacit and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge is the individual and situation exact knowledge of an individual that exists in the social mind, performance, and observation (Duffy 2000). Tacit knowledge is tough to express as it is articulated complete action-based talents and cannot be condensed to rules and guidelines. It is intensely deep-rooted in actions, commitment, principles, values and it can only be ultimately accessed (Baloh et al., 2011). Tacit knowledge is extremely personal, individual, hard to reinforce, expressive and communicate fully, knowledge based, contextualized, job precise, moved over discussion or description, not taken by official teaching or exercise and may even be hidden but talented of attractive explicit information (Nonka and Takeuchi, 1995, Hislop, 2013).

2.1.1 Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is basically a discipline that has been the main opinion of discussion from the last few decades. Knowledge management as a discipline has been a focal point of discussion over the past few decades. In recent years, the position of knowledge management has remained extensively familiar as the fundamentals of commercial economies moved from ordinary capitals to intellectual or knowledgeable assets. Since 1995 the eruption in the literature environment brings the emerging idea of knowledge management. In soul knowledge management is valuable to all areas, be it informative or educational, banking, communications, manufacture/industrial, and even the municipal sectors. Many groups have understood that technology-based competitive advantages are passing and that the only defensible competitive rewards they have are their workers and so to continue at the lead and continue some competitive advantage organizations must have a good size to remember, advance, establish, and apply their employee capabilities (GroËnhaug and Nordhaug, 1992).

Knowledge management is defined by W.R. King (2008) as the process of plan, organize, inspire or motivate, and controlling of processes, systems, and people in the organization and confirm that the knowledge-related effects are enhanced and efficiently engaged. According to the definition T. Shanhong (2000), Knowledge management is "effective finding, formation, development, resolving, use, storage, and distribution of knowledge in command to create an attitude for the conversion of tacit knowledge in explicit

knowledge." Jashapara (2004) expresses knowledge management in the system of a four-looped procedure as Creating, forming, distributing or sharing (both tacit and explicit knowledge) and applying of knowledge.

According to the definition of O. Nazari (2003), Knowledge Creating is a boundless procedure which comprises making novel ideas, clutching novel paradigms, and uniting lonely principles for founding new procedures. Knowledge Organizing is the twist of knowledge management sequence refers to the storage, recording, and protective knowledge in arrangements and edges which lease other staffs recover it. (Radding, 2003, pp178-189). Knowledge Sharing is a mutual knowledge graceful and trickle amongst people and mechanical and non-mechanical centers for knowledge. In fact, 90% of the knowledge management achievement rests on correct knowledge sharing. (Radding, 2003, pp. 160); and knowledge implementing consists of using the gotten ideas and knowledge, deprived of being worried about their announcers H. Benbya (2008).

2.1.2 *Knowledge sharing*

Knowledge sharing considered as an essential strategy for increasing innovation at the organizational level (Li et al., 2013). Chang et al., in 2012 stated that knowledge sharing is strongly affecting the performance of the organization in a competitive environment. So abundant of efforts have been made to discover the aspects that raise knowledge sharing at the organizational level (Wand et al., 2010). Connelly et al. (2012, p65) explain the situation in which an individual involved in active and planned knowledge hiding. According to them, knowledge hiding is basically "a planned attitude by an individual to disguise or withhold knowledge that is demanded by another person". So, it's a problem of mindset and the way an individual think. There are many individuals who didn't seek out any contact and knowledge discussions. They avoid telling their colleagues about what they know or learned, that's a problem they did not realize the importance of knowledge sharing. According to Kidwell (2000), knowledge sharing is the basic purpose of the presence of universities. Few studies in the field of knowledge management in academics focus on various themes. In the study of Nawi et. al (2012), they explained that the process of knowledge management among academicians contains "knowledge capturing, knowledge organizing, refining and transferring".

2.1.3 *Knowledge hiding*

It is becoming more clear that at any level individual is unwilling to share knowledge level when organizational tracks are planned to perform or to help the transfer of knowledge. This research will focus to find the relationship between the major constructs of knowledge hoarding, knowledge sharing, knowledge hiding and knowledge transferability, etc. According to Davenport and Prusak (1998, p. 5), Knowledge is "a mix of experience, principles, information, and expert understandings that offer framework for evaluating new practices and information" Connelly et.al (2012) defines knowledge hiding as silencing, withholding or secreting of task data, ideas, and Experience. Knowledge hiding also indicates that a singular will provide less than the full power to funding to organizational knowledge (Lin and Huang, 2010). Connelly et.al in his study of 2009 stated that knowledge hiding behavior is more dominated because of the strong role of competitions but in knowledge sharing behavior knowledge transferability was very strong.

Husted et.al 2002 articulated few of the reasons behind the knowledge hoarding including Knowledge sources may reserve knowledge because of the number of reasons that may include the individual feeling of their personal value or accomplishments in the sense of ownership, an individual may avoid knowledge sharing because of taking it as a burden and a responsibility to convey to others in addition to the routine tasks, bosses and managers may avoid knowledge sharing because they want to maintain power on subordinates, one more reason for lack of knowledge sharing is may be fear of hosting or presenting the knowledge by putting less struggle towards his or her development. Connelly et.al 2012 stated that the reason for hiding behavior is might be laziness. Servin et al., 2005 pointed out that the reason behind the knowledge hiding is may be related to a cultural factor, so they elaborated that the barriers behind knowledge sharing are may be individually considered that "knowledge itself a power". "I can't trust on others", employees are facing a shortage of time". "you take others idea and then move towards taking credit

of that”, “few may consider that it’s not my job,” “it’s considered as another management fashion”, etc. Peng in 2013 focused to find that why and when is knowledge hiding prominent in employees? and answered that there are strong feelings of psychological ownership of knowledge.

Studies of Cerne et al., 2014, Connelly et al., 2015 specified that knowledge hiding is not just to increase your own benefit but it is also held back a coworker’s performance. In business surroundings, employees found themselves as in direct competition for promotions, incentives and as well as for the achievement of incentives. (Kilduff et al., 2010) concluded that coworkers or colleagues are considered as a threat to one’s own valuable results. Competitions between colleagues may be move so forcefully that it may set a blind motivation that led towards counterproductive behavior of workers. In the highly personal environment where goals of an individual have a priority over the shared goals, knowledge hiding is considered as an active matter to either achieve a competitive edge over colleagues or maybe to get appreciated outcomes like a promotion or financial resource, etc. Yoon et.al 2000 concluded that colleagues or coworkers are the individuals who work at a workplace together and they take positions or grades similar to each other.

Knowledge sharing and knowledge hiding both can’t be opposite but their constructs are related and distinct (Connelly et al., 2012; Connelly et al., 2015; Demir kasimoglu, 2015; Peng, 2013). The construct of knowledge hiding is comprised of 3 basic elements includes: evasive hiding, rationalized hiding and playing dumb. Evasive knowledge hiding is a condition in which a provider of knowledge may provide incorrectly as well as asmisleading information and making a promise to provide a complete answer that he or she has planned and envisioned to provide. Rationalized hiding is the condition in which the provider of the knowledge give explanation and reasons for sharing the requested knowledge by the colleagues and moved this blame to the third party, for example the information is confidential and not allowed to the any other third party etc., another element of knowledge hiding is playing dumb in which the knowledge hider act as to pretend the situation of the relevant knowledge that is requested by the subordinate, e.g. I have no idea about a requested knowledge.

Numerous reasons of knowledge hiding of employees are stated which includes distrust, task relatedness, the complexity of knowledge and the climate of knowledge sharing. (Connelly et al., 2012, Webster et al., 2008), the culture of the organization (Webster et al., 2008), personality of an individual as well as work environment (Demirkasimoglu, 2015; Nerstad, 2014), interdependency of the goals (Lam & Bavik, 2015), complexity in knowledge (Pan & Zhang, 2014) as well as laziness (Webster et al., 2008) etc. on the other hand there are less efforts to check the behavioral intentions effect according to theory of planned behavior towards knowledge hiding perspective. The purpose of this research will be to focus on the behavioral intentions of an individual towards knowledge hiding behavior.

Connelly et al in 2012 state that it’s needed to focus on the differences between knowledge sharing, knowledge hoarding, co productive workplace behavior, etc. The main purpose of this research is to explain the reasons behind knowledge hiding. As mentioned earlier in the study of Michailova, 2002 the knowledge hiding behavior take form according to the graded or hierarchal situations. This study will contribute to investigating the factors that are affecting the knowledge hiding. De Long et al (2000) stated that the basic reasons behind lack of knowledge sharing’s are maybe non-supportive organizational culture and as well as lack of incentive motivations behind workers knowledge sharing.

2.1.4 Knowledge based view (KBV)

KBV (Knowledge-based view) of an organization or a firm assumes that a firm renders services obtainable or offered by using knowledge. The knowledge is entrenched and embedded in as well it is approved through many entities that also includes organizational identity, culture documents, individual employees, routines and policies, etc. (Grant 1996). According to the knowledge-based view, the knowledge is considered as a most powerful as well as having a significant source for an organization and this vies is fitting towards the software industry as they are providing the IT services. Concentrating upon knowledge perspective as a main creative resource, KBV reflects the dare of the direction for KM is to plan devices

over and done with the knowledge resources of different persons that can be organized in the manufacture of a particular product or service (Grant 2013).

2.2 Coworker's Relationship

Somayeh labafi (2017) shown a qualitative learning around knowledge hiding and discover that welcoming or friendly relationships and knowledge hiding both are contrariwise to each other, rare encryptions of this study have been explained that "At the start of work, I set up that if I notice my individual professional and not intersect with others I would more recognize, so that is properly what I confirmed." Few other encryptions or codes of this revision specifies that "If I advance systems as well as network with my coworkers or colleagues, they may have requirements that I cannot carry. Colleagues naturally have difficulties that unused time; therefore, I struggle to consume the least communication done with them."

The term Coworkers is defined by Yoon et.al. (2000) "they are the persons who work in a composed way at a workplace and also grip a position, situation or a job status parallel to one another". It's noticeable that the communication among the coworkers carries a significant effect on organizational utilities. Hodson (1997) clarified that the coworker or colleague's relationship carries four significant purposes; the association among coworkers are significant for job-related socialization, e.g. coworkers might shadow their apprentices and also recover the suggestion in the direction of an occupation. Secondly in case of a positive relationship among coworkers happen it conveys a unitary within the organization, e.g. coworkers custom a defending plan against each other as well as towards their managers, administrators, supervisors, etc. thirdly in case of resistance in contradiction of those who are an expert witness or authority the coworkers relationship stuffs a lot and at fourth the objective is the relationship with coworkers tolerate or affirm group characteristics. Hondson fundamentally enlarged that in the situation of a conflict or battle with coworkers and solidarity, they both are imperative for the management of the relationship, job satisfaction and the knowledge of having a meaningful as well as an impressive work. Hodson further expounded a significant result among coworker's relationship and improved relationship in the direction of management.

In case of a positive relationship with coworker's it carries a positive influence on workplace and various individual outcomes furthermore in case of a negative relation with coworker then it will negatively affect in the direction of workplaces as well as various individual results of an employee at the workplace. Exactly with a positive relationship among coworker then it will decrease the level of psychological disorders like stress and burnout that are linked to the job. (Fry & Barker, 2002; Koeske & Koeske, 1989), Besides a poor relationship between coworker primes to condensed job satisfaction, results in the relationship among employee and management extra weaker or it also declined efficiency (Hodson, 1997; Jehn, 1995).

2.2.1. Theory of attachment

According to this theory a person sense of an ideal balance among closeness to and a gap or distance from the vital people from his or her life. (Ainsworth & Bowlby, 1991). An attachment theory aim is to explain the effective bonding that people make towards each other individual. (Smith, Murphy, & Coats, 1999). An attachment is a shallow, deep as well as a continuing expressive or emotional bond between people that continues through time and space (Ainsworth, 1969; Bowlby, 1969). Attachments may be mutual but are frequently one-way. They contain precise behaviors, like a desire to devote time in the closeness of the individual with whom anyone may have an attachment in the situation of when one feels disappointed, afraid, or exposed (Bowlby, 1969).

An individual's attachment model also specifies that it can influence his or her career and workplace operational activities (Wright & Perrone, 2008). Individuals who had protected attachments incline to see other individuals as innocent trusty and themselves as worth loving as well they are able to control or cope with demanding events (Buelow, Lyddon, & Johnson, 2002). The individuals who had a strong attachment or trust others but not themselves, have low self-esteem, need reassurance as well as they required praise, jerk left when getting a response, and choose jobs based on salary, which also results to have a low job as

well as career satisfaction. Attachment representations remained to start to be connected to helping others in their turnover intentions, as well as emotional regulation (Richards & Schat, 2011).

2.3 Entrepreneurial Intentions

Entrepreneurship Godfather Eisenman (2013) describes entrepreneurship as “the pursuit of opportunity beyond resources controlled” it is not just funding towards the creation of new venture but also focused on the growth of plans in hand. Dress (1996) stated that Entrepreneurship makes improvement for the social and technological growth of a particular country. Gorman et al (1997) observed a strong relationship among economic development and entrepreneurial education. Brown et al (2002) stated that the students who get entrepreneurial guidance and knowledge are more possible to project into practice. Moen and Kolvereid (1997) concluded that formal learning of a student has a great influence on student’s motivation towards real world entrepreneurship as a professional preference. That’s why entrepreneurship understanding is highlighted in higher educational institutes and suggest courses related to it as a part of the scheme of studies. Entrepreneurship reflecting the most important way for the progress of an economy either it’s developed or developing.

Entrepreneurship requires time, efforts and actual planning, no doubt risks are the part of it along with the chances of opportunities. An entrepreneurial business is started with a unique idea and purpose of the concerned entrepreneurs, which few motivate them to toreach the goals. (Franke, 2003; Giacomini et al., 2011). Few researchers of Linen (2008) Chen ((1998) concluded that entrepreneurship is linked with psychological and motivational factors that comprise of probably of new technologies, venture opportunities, self-efficacy, and the tendency to innovate. Mazzarol (2007) explains that this process involves skills to share, risk taking, on time decision making and as well as confidence level. Aslam et al in 2012 conducted a research to check the level of Entrepreneurship intentions by using a theory of Ajzen’s TPB and entrepreneurial questionnaire of Autio et al (2001), they conducted this study among 300 students of students enrolled in universities of the Punjab and proves that entrepreneurial education influence of an individual towards entrepreneurship. They further elaborated that gender also has a significant impact on this intention Male take more interest in the opening of new ventures as compared to the female. Mazzatol (2007) conducted research among 112 MBA students and explained this phenomenon, from 112 samples he observed that 56 students are studying entrepreneurship as a course in MBA programmed and an overall score of students was low as compared to the entrepreneurs in the perspective of risk taking, creativity, etc.

Wu Wu (2012) defined the term entrepreneurship that “it’s an individual personal desire for the startup of a new venture or the addition of values within an existing venture” Gelderen et al in 2008 stated that the intentions of entrepreneurship are derived from spacious intentions. In the research of Quan (2012) he explained that the intentions related to entrepreneurship can be divided into two terms deliberate (it concerned with the behavior of an entrepreneur for the run-up of a new venture because of the availability of entrepreneurial behavior) and impulsive (it elaborates the intentions towards unplanned and unrecognized control of resources of business).

Skills and competencies also play an important role in the development of student’s intentions and entrepreneurship. Basically, talent motivates an individual to the startup of a new or creative thing. Many of the researches explained a significant relationship between student’s skills and abilities and entrepreneurship intentions. Defra in 2008 identified that in business skills competency is one of the factors that leads you towards diversification in business as well as the profitability of a business. Furthermore, for managing a business excellently an entrepreneur should require a diversifying ability. Chen et al (1998) argue that skills have a signifying impact on the intentions of entrepreneurship. A study of Linan (2008) declared that there is a strong relationship exists between the skills of individual and behavior, those individuals who have a high level of entrepreneurial skills and abilities are more confident and track entrepreneurial activities.

2.3.1 Theory of planned behavior (TPB)

Theory of planned-behavior is acknowledged as the finest theory for determining an individual's attitude as well as behavior. Rendering to this philosophy the humanoid behavior and intents are focused toward three things, attitude to a particular behavior (it comprises of the favorable or unfavorable actions or attitudes to the behavior that might be well-thought-out as a positive or negative consequence; e.g. if I drive a decision then what would be the consequences? What would be the encouraging outcomes as well as undesirable outcomes of this pronouncement or conduct?), subjective standards (this is also recognized as a normative certainty that is marked due to social compression or as some idiosyncratic standards, e.g. what others are imagining for me to do? How they are imagining from me to perform?) Moreover, behavior control (Also known as a behavioral control element by emphasizing on the performance of that specific behavior, e.g. do I have the indispensable knowledge to spot the choice or verdict?).

When mutual, attitudes to the behavior, subjective norm as well as the behavioral control are leading, they result in the creation of an intention known as behavioral intentions that brings change in the attitude of the behavior of an individual. An individual is more possible to have a strong behavior if they have an encouraging attitude or purposes towards the behavior. An individual intention towards a behavior is stronger in the case when the above mentioned three things are strongly correlated rather than alone. So, these intentions lead to a change in the behavior of an individual. It might be possible that many of the external barriers restrict or control an individual for performing an action even that an individual has an intention to do so.

The philosophy of planned behavior is functional attitude and behavior association that also encountered success in forecasting the diversity of behaviors to some degree. (Ajzen, 1988, Godin & Kok, 1996). It provides a feature of an individual intents and decision to see specific conduct. (Manstead & Parker, 1995; Sutton, 1998). Intent means an individual's inspiration in the acts of his or her choice to put exertions to behave. Intentions and behavior are supposed to be mightily associated when measured at an equal of specificity on the way to act or mark, situation, and time span (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Attitude up to a careful behavior smear its impact on conduct through intents. In suggesting the conduct is merely below the controller of intent, the TRA (theory of reasoned action) bounds to volitional acts or arrangements. Behaviors challenging, possessions, or chances not freely accessible, assistance is not measured to be hidden under the area of the practicability of the TRA or are probable to be sick prediction by the TRA (Fishbein, 1993).

According to the theory of reasoned actions, the attitude is measured as the forecaster of individual conduct. Attitude is the fundamentally overall evaluations of the specific behavior. TRA also necessitates subjective customs by way of the other reason for intents. Subjective standards entail an individual's views around whether significant others purpose he or she must encompass in the compartment. Substantial others are the persons whose partialities around a person's conduct in this area are noteworthy to him or her. Idiosyncratic norms are predictable to portion the social masses to attain or not to attain or achieve a specific performance. TPB comprises of a third forecaster of intents, PBC (perceived behavioral control). Henceforth, social or interactive intent is a determination of three direct grounds of factors well-thought-out as a determinant: attitudes, subjective norms, and PBC. According to Ajzen's (1985) early performances of the TPB suggested that PBC or intents would interconnect in their conjectures or prophecies of conduct such that determinations or intentions developed a stronger forecaster of behavior as PBC augmented. On the foundation of the above literature, there are few research gaps that no one has premeditated these among these constructs, so the research propositions are given as;

- If rationalized hiding is increasing, then Entrepreneurial intentions are decreasing.
- If evasive hiding is increasing, then entrepreneurial intentions are decreasing.
- If dumb playing is increasing, then entrepreneurial intentions are decreasing

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

According to Connelly et al., (2012), "knowledge is power". In 1990 the attention towards the concept of knowledge management in various organizational surroundings arises significantly. In the field of

management sciences, economics, information sciences, and sociology the knowledge transfer and knowledge sharing are most commonly researched issues for professionals and academic dissertation. In spite of the efforts to improve knowledge, knowledge sharing in organizational achievement has been an abstract (KM Wiig, 1997). Many of the studies related to knowledge management thought focused out the deficiencies of knowledge hiding aspects according to various work dimensions. (E.g. Greenberg, Brinsfield and Edwards, 2007; Webster, Brown, Zweig, Connelly, Connelly, et al., 2012). Moreover, Michailova and Husted (2002) declared that assistants hoard knowledge by supposing that managers or superiors are hate assistants who show more knowledge as compared to themselves. By focusing on this type of opinions there is more need to study knowledge hiding perspective by empirically, for that reason the Companies that work or run in the software industry are knowledge-based that are powerfully innovation demanding. The environment of their processes involves that their employees should be talented, brilliant and own great level of knowledge. The distribution or sharing of knowledge in such organizations are energetic or vital to keeping the firm in competition in an extremely competitive industry (Bari, et al. 2016; Chen et al., 2016). Connelly et al in 2012 state that it's needed to focus on the differences between knowledge sharing, knowledge hoarding, co productive workplace behavior, etc. On the other hand, there is an absence of examination of knowledge hiding in a software industry level. So, in this study researcher will put on the knowledge hiding behavior as an obstacle towards the entrepreneurship intentions of employees in the software industry. By this detail, this study will deliver extra knowledge to the academic community as well as will contribute towards the decision-making and applied implications which will be discussed in the conclusion section.

4. OBJECTIVES BEHIND THIS STUDY AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The basic objective of this research study is to explain how knowledge hiding behavior among employees is related to entrepreneurial intentions.

- What is the correlation between knowledge hiding dimensions and Entrepreneur Intentions construct?
- How coworker's relationship is mediating the direct impact of RH and EI?

Earlier revisions have stated correlations among personality and knowledge management (e.g. Matzler, et.al 2008; Wang et.al 2007). Meanwhile, personality characters found related to knowledge sharing, the relationship amid knowledge hiding and entrepreneurial intentions appeared to be value investigating.

Figure1; Theoretical Framework

H1; RH has a significant influence on EI

H2: PD has a significant influence on EI.

H3: EH has a significant influence on EI.

H4; CR mediates the relationship between RH and EI.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research design and paradigm

The essential motivation of research methodology is to elucidate in detail that in what was a study or an exploration is happening, all of methods, procedures and the measures that the investigator is using throughout the analysis of constructs of specific study (Saunders et.al, 2009).

Rendering to Bryman et.al (2014) paradigm is explained as credence and fundamentals for an investigator in the specific study that impacts, what is a must that needs to be explored, and how the consequences are going to be construed as well as by what means this should be accomplished. Hence the methodology that is used in this study is focused on two paradigms including ontology (a belief about we grip about the natural existence and being) and epistemology (a belief that we also have knowledge about the nature) analysis that are considered as two different angles for seeing the philosophy of the research. This study is centered on the ontological analysis as it is suitable for the investigation of the human behavior as well as for its computations on an arrangement of the belief that reflects a clarification about an individual or what organizes a fact. According to Bryman et.al (2014) in deduction the researcher investigates hypothesis according to the existing theories and then convert or transfer it to operational relations or terms that are considered more common and suitable in quantitative research but in induction approach the results of the study is rely on suggestions and implications of the results according to the theories and explains how results are responding to the overhead stated knowledge as well as theories. To establish a relationship between social research and theory, two main approaches known as inductive and deductive are used.

5.2 Target Population and Unit of Analysis

The target population of this study is the employees working in the software industry of Pakistan. In this study software industry is chosen as it is considered as a creation or a source of knowledge hub through innovations. Our unit of analysis is the employees of the software industry of Pakistan, as they are more aware of the entrepreneurial intentions as well as their strategies towards the hiding of the knowledge.

5.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size contains 205 employees (grounded on regression supposition of Heir et.al 2007, 5 respondents compared to 1 measured item) of diverse employees working in IT sector firms. Secondly, non-probability sampling is used in this research study as well as a convenience method of sampling for the target population.

5.4 Instrument development

Data is collected by structuring a questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly disagree 1, Disagree 2, Neutral 3, Agree 4 and Strongly Agree 5). This questionnaire consists of the well thought questions, with a total of 29 questions sliced into 4 parts:

- Part 1 is focused on discussing Demographics
- Part 2 is focused on knowledge hiding, questions adopted from the study of (Connelly et.al, 2012, $\alpha = .85$).
- Part 3 consists of discussing entrepreneurial intentions, questionnaire for measuring three variables of entrepreneurial intentions includes Personal attitude, perceived behavior control, and subjective norms are adapted from the studies of (Francisco Liñán and Yi-Wen Chen 2009. Autio et al., 2001, Autio et al., 1997)
- Part 4 consist of the coworker's relationship, questions adopted from the study of Hain 2003

5.6 Methods of Data Analysis

Mediation analysis is carried out by using PROCESS macro on IBM SPSS.

6. RESEARCH FINDINGS

6.1 Demographics Analysis

The demographics evidence have been composed of few areas includes gender and age, etc. findings dictate' out of 205 respondents 69 % were male and the remaining 31% were female. Respondents' age varies with 30% were >30 years, and 59 % are having age level between 30-40 years and remaining were 40 above. Table 1 is screening the descriptive data of the current revision. The motive of descriptive statistics is on the complete to clarify the facts, it delivers instant of data specifics. To approach in the normality of the data researcher carry out a descriptive investigation that comprises mean, standard deviation, and kurtosis as well skewness.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std.Error
Gender	205	1.47	.500	.134	.168	-1.999	.313
Age	205	1.70	.668	.441	.168	-.768	.313
Education	205	2.12	.636	-.102	.168	-.551	.313
experience	205	1.85	.802	.730	.168	.078	.314
Valid N	205						

Reliability specifies the interior uniformity of measure items. Payot (1991) guaranteed that the support of measure scripts a superior of internal consistency if the significance of Cronbach's alpha is .85.in existing study all the adjustable reliability coefficients are practically near about this high-quality value, which specify the worthy reliability of the scale. Correlation stretches a description of the category of the relationship among variables. Coetzee in 2003 specified that when the researcher spotting the association amongst variables, its superior value of magnitude designates a positive or sturdy linear association between the variables. Table 2 is presentation the noteworthy relationship among the variables.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. RH	1			
2. EH	.349**	1		
3. PD	.278**	.254**	1	
4. EI	(.278)**	(.254)**	(.278)**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The value of R² is .541 explains that the linear regression is contributing 54.1% of the variation in the data. The statistics with RH (Beta = .45, p < 0.01) are a significant forecaster of EI of individual employees. A higher level of RH will outcome the upper level of employee's individual knowledge behind entrepreneurship. Nowadays Knowledge hiding is an upcoming wonder in work surroundings (Peng, 2013). Babcock (2004) specified that Fortune 500 organizations lose almost USD 31.5 billion per year by inadequate or failing to inspire its labors to share or transfer knowledge within entities or organizational settings.

The survey was directed in the United States and China and findings showed that 76 % of US participants stated that they one-time hide knowledge moreover from the respondents in China 46 % admitted they once hide or concealed knowledge (Connelly et.al, 2012; Peng, 2013).

Table 3: Regression Analysis

	β	Se	t	p	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
Rationalized Hiding	0.414	0.048	9.075	0.000	0.3086	0.5209
Playing Dumb	0.211	0.063	4.433	0.000	0.0922	0.3442

Evasive Hiding	0.406	0.048	7.795	0.000	0.3086	0.5209
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DV= Entrepreneurial Intentions

Table 3 explains the regression analysis outcomes. It shows that RH is positively significantly associated with EI. Table shows that RH is significantly positive ($\beta=.414, p<.001$) impact on EI. So H1 of the study get supported by our data. In the same way, PD and EH is also a significant positive relation with EI ($\beta=.211, p<.001$), ($\beta=.406, p<.001$). De Brun and Servin in (2005) stated that individual mostly prefers to take guidance or learn from their peers rather than managers so based on this statement in this research I supposed that the knowledge hiding behavior of software engineers may differ towards their superiors and coworkers. Additionally, Michailova and Husted (2002) declared that assistants purposefully store or hoard knowledge at the believed that managers or bosses dislike the assistants who seem to be extra knowledgeable than themselves. By considering these factors the focus of this research will be towards the target of both superiors as well as coworkers as an empirical part of this research. It was the hypothesis that CR mediates the direct influence of RH towards EI. Mediation analysis was carried out among RH, CR, and EI, using *PROCESS* macro (Hayes, A. F, 2012).

Table4; Mediation Analysis between Rationalize hiding and Entrepreneurial Intentions through Coworkers Relationship (N=205)

Antecedent	Coworkers Relationship			Consequent		
	Coeff.	SE	P	Coeff.	SE	P
Constant	.00	.09	1.00	.00	.07	1.00
RH	.46	.09	.001	.27	.09	.001
CR				.33	.08	.006
Controls						
Gender				.13	.07	.081
Age				.08	.07	.255
	R ² = .300			R ² = .389		
	F (1, 163) = 40.68, P < .001			F (1, 163) = 5.157, P < .001		

Note: Coeff= standardized regression coefficient

Mediation results indicated that RH was found to be a positive significant predictor of CR and EI. Whereas CR was found to be a significant predictor of EI. So, mediation was found to be significant. Indirect effect (effect= .13 bootstrap Interval 4 =.05) However the indirect effect of CR was found to be positively significant between KH and EI.

Figure2; the Statistical Model of Mediation Analysis

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Software organizations are considered as one of the key producers as well as generators of knowledge, so there is need to know that how the knowledge hiding behavior is affecting on their entrepreneurial intentions of employees with superiors and as well as with their coworkers according to the request of the valuable or necessary information from them. Purpose of this study is to give a descriptive picture of knowledge hiding behavior of software engineers and how common this behavior is affecting their innovative intentions to take place. Additional Dawson (2012) stated that companies are providing the business or commercial services that are originated on the request or application of remarkably specialized and particular

knowledge as well as expertise. A business has three central assets: people, the intellectual capital of their individuals that they use for development and relationships with customers which build by their employees (Heller-Schuh & Kasztler, 2005). Presence of knowledge founded is one distinctive characteristic that these three assets are mutual (Heller-Schuh & Kasztler, 2005). Furthermore, throughout investigation of literature concerning with the phenomenon of knowledge hiding it originate that the researches related to knowledge hiding are done related to personality factors (Payal et.al, 2014; Nihan Demirkasımoğlu, 2015) as well as it's also a qualitative study (Payal et.al, 2014) thus the researcher motivation was to conduct quantitative study in order to accompaniment the earlier studies and deliver added visions. Organizational knowledge is recognized as a non-tangible but much appreciated source in the acquisition of competitive advantage. In spite of the numerous struggles to streamline the transfer of knowledge in organizations, remarkable successes have not been achieved (Huang et al., 2008). Companies that work or run in the software industry are knowledge-based that are powerfully innovation demanding. The environment of their processes involves that their employees are talented, brilliant and own great level of knowledge. The distribution, as well as sharing of knowledge in such organizations, are energetic or vital to keeping the firm in competition in an extremely competitive industry (Bari, et al. 2016; Chen et al., 2016).

8. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study targeted just software development sector for sampling but in future other service sectors like education can be targeted. Because knowledge hiding phenomenon is also prevailing in these sectors. Future investigations would also determine the collaborating standards of additional categories of knowledge hiding along with spearhead ethnic diversity towards the reputation of the organization. Comprehensive, our study recommends that both scholars and practitioners should confess the role of coworker towards knowledge sharing. This study contributed to the key variable of knowledge hiding. So, managers should focus on the coworker's relationship that is mediating among RH and EI. If they manage to do better the perceptions of their employees that will lead them towards a supportive organizational work climate. Which are very much important for organizational perspective. The distribution of information or knowledge enables organizations to improve their competitive advantage by innovation.

References

- i. Autio, E., Keeley, R.H., Klofsten, M., Parker, G.G.C., & Hay, M. (2001). *Entrepreneurial intent among students in Scandinavia and in the USA*. *Enterprise & Innovation Management Studies*, 2, (2), 145-161.
- ii. Autio, E., Keeley, R.H., Klofsten, M., & Ulfstedt, T. (1997). *Entrepreneurial intent among students: testing an intent model in Asia, Scandinavia, and USA*. Paper presented at the *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, Wellesley, MA: Babson College. Retrieved June 20, 2004
- iii. Ajzen, I. (1985). *From intentions to action: A theory of planned behavior*. In J. Kuhl & J. Beckman (Eds.), *Action control: From cognitions to behaviors* (pp. 11-39). New York, NY: Springer.
- iv. Ajzen, I. (1988). *Attitudes, personality and behavior*. Milton Keynes, UK: Open University Press. *Theory of Planned Behavior*: <http://people.umass.edu/ajzen/tpb.html> *Sample Questionnaires*: <http://people.umass.edu/ajzen/pdf/tpb.questionnaire.pdf> *A WHO Guide for Developing "Knowledge, Attitude, and Behavior" Surveys*: http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2008/9789241596176_eng.pdf

- v. Allee, V. (1997). 12 Principles of knowledge management. *Training and Development*, 51(11), 71-74.
- vi. Ainsworth, M.D.S. (1969). Object relations, dependency and attachment: A theoretical review of the infant-mother relationship. *Child Development*, 40, 969–1025.
- vii. Ainsworth, M.D.S., & Bowlby, J. (1991, April). An ethological approach to personality development. *American Psychologist*, 46, 333–341.
- A. Jashapara, *Knowledge Management: An Integrated Approach* Harlow, 2004, Essen:Prentice Hall.
- viii. Baloh, P., Desouza, K. C. and Paquette, S. (2011). The concept of knowledge. In: K. C. Desouza and S. Paquette (Eds.), *Knowledge Management: An Introduction* (pp. 35-71). New York: NY: Neal-Schuman Publishers, Inc.
- ix. Bowlby, J. (1969). *Attachment and loss: Vol. 1. Attachment*. New York: Basic Books
- x. Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- xi. Bari, M. W., Fanchen, M., & Baloch, M. A. (2016). The Relationship between Knowledge Management Practices, Innovativeness and Organizational Performance (A Case from Software Industry). *Science International*, 28(1). 463-475.
- xii. Bryman, A. & Bell, E. (2014). *Business research methods*, 3rd edition. Oxford University Press, USA.
- xiii. Baron, R. M. (1986). The Moderator-Mediator Variable Distinction in Social Psychological Research – Conceptual, Strategic, and Statistical Considerations. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 51(6), 1173
- xiv. Baer, M. (2012). Putting creativity to work: The implementation of creative ideas in organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55(5), 1102-1119. doi:10.5465/amj.2009.0470
- xv. Connelly, C.E., Zweig, D., Webster, J. and Trougakos, J.P. (2012), ‘‘Knowledge hiding in organizations’’, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 33 No. 1, pp. 64-88.
- xvi. Chen, X., Zhou, Y., Probert, D., & Su, J. (2016). Managing knowledge sharing in distributed innovation from the perspective of developers: empirical study of open source software projects in China. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 29, 1-22.
- xvii. Černe, M., Nerstad, C. G. L., Dysvik, A., & Škerlavaj, M. (2014). What goes around comes around: Knowledge hiding, perceived motivational climate, and creativity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(1), 172-192. doi:10.5465/amj.2012.0122
- xviii. Davenport, T.H. and Prusak, L. (1998), *Working Knowledge: How Organizations Manage What They Know*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.
- xix. Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief; attitude, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley
- xx. Fishbein, M. (1993). Introduction. In D. J. Terry, C. Gallois, & M. McCamish (Eds.), *The theory of reasorzed action: Its application to AIDS-preventive Behavior* (pp. xv-xxv). Oxford, UK: Pergamum.
- xxi. Epetimehin, F. M. and Ekundayo, O. (2011). Organisational knowledge management: survival strategy for Nigeria insurance industry. *Interdisciplinary Review of Economics and Management*, 1(2), 9-15.
- xxii. GroËnhaug, K. and Nordhaug, O. (1992). Strategy and competence in firms. *European Management Journal*, 10(4), 438-444.
- xxiii. Husted, K. & Michailova, S. (2002). ‘‘Diagnosing and fighting knowledge-sharing hostility’’, *Organizational dynamics*, 31 (1), 60-73.
- xxiv. Hislop, D. (2013). *Knowledge management in organisations: A critical introduction*. 3rd Ed. UK: Oxford University Press.
- xxv. H. Benbya,(2008), *Knowledge management, system implementation, lessons from the silicon valley* Chands Publishing, *International Journal of Knowledge Management*, April-June, 5(2), pp: 103-105.
- xxvi. Heller-Schuh, B. & Kasztler, A. (2005). Analyzing Knowledge Networks in Organizations. In *Proceedings of I-KNOW*, 45-53
- xxvii. Husted, K. & Michailova, S. (2002). ‘‘Diagnosing and fighting knowledge-sharing hostility’’,
- xxviii. Kidwell, J. J., Vander Linde, K. & Johnson, S. L. (2000). Applying Corporate Knowledge Management Practices in Higher Education. *Edu cause quarterly*, 23 (4), 28-35

- xxix. Lin, T.C. and Huang, C.C. (2010), "Withholding effort in knowledge contribution: the role of social exchange and social cognitive on project teams", *Information and Management*, Vol. 47 No. 3, pp. 188-196. *Organizational dynamics*, 31 (1), 60-73. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0090-2616\(02\)00072-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0090-2616(02)00072-4)
- xxx. Huang, X., Gattiker, T. F., & Schwarz, J. L. (2008). Interpersonal trust formation during the supplier selection process: The role of the communication channel. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 44, 53–75.
- xxxi. Miles. Ian, green. Lawrence (2010), Knowledge management and innovation: networks and networking. *Journal of knowledge management*, 14(3). 104-122.
- xxxii. Matzler, K., Renzl, B., Müller, J., Herting, S. & Mooradian, T. A. (2008). Personality traits and knowledge sharing, *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29 (3), 301-313. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2007.06.004>
- xxxiii. Manstead, A. S. R., & Parker, D. (1995). Evaluating and extending the theory of planned behavior. In W. Stroebe & M. Hewstone (Eds.), *European review of social psychology* (Vol. 6, pp. 69-95). Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons.
- xxxiv. Mohayidin, M. G., Azirawani, M.N., Kamuriddin, N. & Idawati, M. M. (2007). The application of knowledge management in enhancing the performance of Malaysian universities. *Electronic journal of knowledge management*, 5 (3), 301-312.
- xxxv. Nonaka, I. and Takeuchi, H. (1995). *The knowledge creating company*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- xxxvi. Nawi, H. S. A., Shukor, N. S. A., Basaruddin, S., Rahim, N. M., Hassan, R. A. & Jusoff, K. (2012). *Determining the Existence of Knowledge Management Processes among Academicians*", *Journal of Knowledge Management Practice*, 13 (2)
- xxxvii. O. Nazari, *Management and transfer of knowledge*, *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Human Resource Development*, 2003, Tehran: Institute for Productivity and Human Resource Studies.
- xxxviii. Peng, H. (2013). Why and when do people hide knowledge? *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 17(3), 398-415. Doi: 10.1108/JKM-12-2012-0380
- xxxix. Richards, D. A., & Schat, A.C.H. (2011). Attachment at (not to) work: Applying attachment theory to explain individual behavior in organizations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96, 169–182.
- xl. Smith, E. R., Murphy, J., & Coats, S. (1999). Attachment to groups: Theory and measurement. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77, 94–110. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2007). *Research Methods for Business Students*. UK: Pearson Education.
- xli. Sveiby, K. E. (1997). *The new organizational wealth: Managing and measuring knowledge based assets*. San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers, Inc.
- xlii. Servin, G. & De Brun, C. (2005). *ABC of knowledge management: NHS National Library for Health: Specialist Library*.
- xliii. T. Shanhong, *Knowledge management in libraries in the 21st century*. Paper presented at the 66th IFLA council and general conference, 2000\
- xliv. Wiig, K. M. (1997). Knowledge management: an introduction and perspective. *Journal of knowledge Management*, 1(1), 6-14.
- xlv. Witten Baum, G. M., Hollingshead, A. B., & Botero, I. C. (2004). From cooperative to motivated information sharing in groups: Moving beyond the hidden profile paradigm. *Communication Monographs*, 71, 286–310.
- xlvi. Wang, C. C. & Yang, Y. J. (2007). Personality and intention to share knowledge: An empirical study of scientists in an R&D laboratory. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 35 (10), 1427-1436
- xlvii. Wright, S. L., & Perrone, K. M. (2008). The impact of attachment and career-related variables. *Journal of Career Development*, 35, 87–106.
- xlviii. W.R. King , T.R. Chung , M.N. Honey, *Knowledge management and organizational learning*, *international journal of management science*, 2008, OMEGA, Vol.36, p. 168.
- xliv. Yukl, G., Kim, H., & Falbe, C. M. (1996). Antecedents of influence outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81,309–317.